

OPERAS-D

DESIGN FOR OPEN ACCESS PUBLICATIONS IN EUROPEAN
RESEARCH AREAS FOR SOCIAL SCIENCES AND HUMANITIES

Developing network and e-infrastructure strategy

Report on online survey on optimizing e-infrastructure

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Report on online survey on optimizing e-infrastructure

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I. Executive summary

A. Objective

The online survey is part of task 2.2 “Network building” of the Work Package “Developing network and e-infrastructure strategy”. More precisely, the OPERAS-D GA states that “the survey will be based on findings of the landscape study and will contribute towards gaining actual information on practices that will contribute to e-infrastructure integration across Europe.”

Based on the findings of the Landscape study, the main objective of the survey is to have detailed and statistical information on the current practices and collect suggestions regarding open scholarly communication. The survey is meant to identify the gaps in the existing academic publishing ecosystem and verify how well the OPERAS RI is actually addressing the needs of the community. The findings will then serve as a basis to adjust or adapt the building parts of OPERAS.

There were two sessions of the OPERAS surveys: one during Spring 2017¹ (May-June), one during Autumn (Nov.-Dec.). The first session collected general information about the practices in open scholarly communication, information then refined through the second session, which was containing more open questions in order to get as detailed information as possible from the interviewees.

As part of the Network building, the survey for the publishers also contained the proposition to join the OPERAS consortium. Eight publishers showed interest for this proposition.

B. Method

The surveys were spread online using the Limesurvey software and differentiated for each type of stakeholders directly concerned by the construction of the OPERAS RI. The Autumn surveys were addressed to the publishers, the libraries and the funders. Responses from the researchers during the Spring were sufficient in quantity and quality and didn't require further investigation. The socio-economic actors' survey hasn't been made again either because they seemed to remain a bit difficult to reach at this stage.

In order to increase the chances of receiving more and more detailed responses, the surveys were sent to specific individuals identified by the Consortium's partners. Nevertheless, as in the first session of the surveys, the link has also been spread on the web and through specific announcements (OPERAS website and social media, mailing list LaLIST).

¹ Report on the Spring survey at <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1009558> , part of the OPERAS Design Study at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1009543> .

C. Topics

While the Spring surveys' structure was based on the OPERAS Working Groups, with the Autumn surveys we have tried to organize the questions with respect to the specific workflow of each community. However, we kept the questions related to OPERAS new platforms and those related to the companion project HIRMEOS² on advanced services.

The main topics for the publishers were the following:

- general activity: domains and types of publications, open access policies, business models
- editing and publishing: production workflow, publishing software, tools and formats
- enrichment and dissemination: metadata, platforms and advanced services
- multilingualism: technical and intellectual aspects
- OPERAS new services

The main topics for the libraries were the following:

- OA support: helpdesk, repository, funding
- OA management in the library: indexing, cataloguing, communication to users
- OA publishing: discovery through DOAJ/DOAB, quality assessment
- advanced services: metrics, online annotations
- OPERAS new services

The main topics for the funders were the following (same as in Spring):

- OA policies and recommendations
- OA providers and publishers
- OPERAS new services

The dissemination, the type of questions and the structure of the questionnaire helped to gather detailed answers by giving space to the interviewees for descriptions based on their experience and workflow.

² HIRMEOS website: <http://www.hirmeos.eu/>

II. Overview

A. Participation

Congruent with the effort to reach identified persons rather than the entire web, the overall participation isn't very high. The small number of answers is also probably due to the fact that the OPERAS network had already been mobilized during the Spring surveys.

For the publishers, we received 21 responses (4 only partial). For the libraries, we received 36 responses (17 only partial). For the funders, although we were looking for a panel of approximately 10 agencies, we couldn't manage to collect more than 5 answers.

B. Countries

Even if the distribution by country doesn't reflect the real composition of the OPERAS consortium, it surely illustrates where are the more articulated OA communities within the same consortium. Netherlands, Germany and France are the countries from which we received more answers for both the publishers (for a total of 52%) and the libraries (for a total of 59%). Although less interested by these surveys, other countries of the consortium have sent some answers (Italy, Portugal, Greece, UK). Another interesting data is the willingness to answer from countries where the OPERAS partners still have little or no activity. This is the case of Switzerland in the libraries surveys. This is also the case of countries somewhat peripheral to OPERAS centre of gravity, especially from north or eastern Europe (Lithuania, Norway, Sweden).

The reason for the rather low statistics is probably also to be found in the choice to provide open questions: requiring a higher engagement from the interviewee, they surely were kind of selective. However, these open questions are also the reason why we have received some very detailed answers, like we will see hereafter.

Participation by country (Europe): Publishers

Participation by country (Europe): Libraries

III. Publishers

As for the open access publishers, a preliminary remark should be that scattered actors imply a scattered landscape. In fact, in parallel to the interest for integrated services, there is also a need for centralized and dedicated information. On the other hand, despite obvious differences, we found some common characteristics in the publishers. There is a certain level of maturity, especially regarding standards, which has to be extended and improved. There is also a positive attitude precisely towards potential improvements to achieve: this is how we could analyze the expectations about training, the interest for structured formats or even advanced and new services.

A. Typology

The first question about the publications' scientific domains shows that if the SSH publishers represent a strong community (47% publish only in SSH), an equal number publish both in SSH and in STEM (47%). This shows the adequation of OPERAS definition, which is to provide services and networking first to the SSH community, before their extension to other scientific communities in STEM.

For the types of publication, it appears there is even less specialization. Among the publishers of our survey, a large majority publishes both journals and books (60%). More so, some of them indicated they also publish grey literature and other specific types (sheet music, enhanced forms of document). Even if these are not the most numerous cases, they

show that OPERAS RI should be able to address these specific challenges in a near future.

Which type of document do you publish?

As far as their business models are concerned, our publishers show more diversity. If the fragmentation of the OA landscape can be considered as a reliable result of the OPERAS Design Study, we have here other elements to illustrate this specificity. The question about business models allowed for multiple answers and the result is an average of 2 financing sources for each publisher. The final chart shows that, even with slightly different amounts, there are in fact three major coexisting models: revenues on sale (65%), BPC/APC (53%), OA institutional funding (47%).

What is your business model?

If one shouldn't be surprised that publishing, like other businesses, uses all the possible options to finance its activity, it's interesting to see that the three main options in this case are almost at the same level. This might be a sign that none of these models would be sustainable by itself and that the publishers have to compensate one by the other. Such business models seem therefore to be more empirical choices than elaborate solutions.

This lack of definition may also explain why the suggestions regarding the potential role of OPERAS in this matter cover very different aspects of the publishing business:

- dissemination: tools and support for wider and better dissemination
- information to authors: providing a list of publishers with their publishing options
- funding: organizing institutional funding or providing information on funding

Other suggestions concerned publishing tools. In fact, among all the suggestions not one is actually about the business models and on how to choose one. This can surprise when the comments show that financing seems sometimes difficult, sometimes rather complex. It seems that if the role of the OPERAS RI in this case is not clear for the publishers, it's also because the issues with business models are not really put in prospect. And this, precisely justifies the work currently made by the OPERAS Business Models Working Group, especially regarding the constitution of a business models marketplace.

Except for some specific cases, the access policies present a rather uniform landscape with a majority of full open access (12 out of 19 responses). In most cases there are no limitations based on types nor any kind of embargo. However, like it was possible to infer from the business models description, the details of the access policies can vary in a significant way. Between those who declare they “offer different options at different prices” and those who provide “full open access immediately”, we also find some publishers who provide OA only for funded publications and others who rely on funders or authors wishes.

More generally, this relates to the definition of open access, which ranges from free usage to gratis access. In fact, the free licenses question seems to describe the same landscape.

Do you have a free licensing policy and which are the free licenses you are using?

The practices or at least the policies are in majority in favor of the most open licenses (35% of CC-BY plus 26% of CC-BY-NC). It is worth noting that more open often means higher fees. And this is in fact one of the reasons of the difficulty to use the more open CC licenses: “CC-BY fees, especially for books, are beyond the budgets most authors have access to”. Other main reasons are:

- fighting unfair commercial use (republishing without attribution),
- tracking the use of the publications,
- scholars’ reluctance and copyright issues (both a problem of free licensing knowledge and of third-parties complex copyright),
- protection of personal data.

Even if this overview shows an indisputable maturity of OA publishing in terms of policies

and flexibility, it also reveals a lack of general structuration. The potential role of OPERAS RI on these topics could be significant, even if it will appear more clearly as far as the publishing process is concerned.

B. Editing and publishing

A small third of the publishers states they are satisfied with their workflow. For the others, the challenges are of different types, sometimes cumulative, always related somehow:

- human resources: the publishers are often small teams with respect to the amount of work (editing or website maintenance),
- technical: passing through different steps with different tools makes the whole process less smooth,
- training: the structured formats (XML, LateX) are not well known or handled.

In fact, like in the Spring surveys, we have the confirmation that the publishing process, in most cases, relies on Microsoft (Word) and Adobe (Indesign) products, and still is, in that sense, based on the print era workflow (manuscript - copy - publication). This is indeed partly reflected by the input and output formats charts. A 94% uses DOC/DOCX files in input and also a 94% produces a PDF in output - when only 40% produces HTML output.

In your publishing workflow, what are the main formats for input data/documents?

In your publishing workflow, what are the main formats for output data/documents?

Nevertheless, this shouldn't hide the fact that (many) other tools are currently used. Besides Open Journal Systems, we also find mentions of Lodel, Hyperwave, LateX, XML-Spy, Sigil. Some publishers didn't even list all the software they use.

The reasons that led the publishers to choose their software give more details about this situation. For making their choice of software, the publishers mention the lack of information on publishing tools made even worse by the constant shift affecting the software, the few number of stable open source software and the lack of advanced skills (e.g. for XML). There are in fact a lot of "by default" choices, where the solution is to use well known tools (OJS) or to externalize the publishing process. However, another group of publishers with more technical agility manages a clear workflow with dedicated tools. Here is one example of this group who uses:

- Indesign as the leading software
- PressBooks to try online production system for authors
- OJS to publish OA journals
- Sigil as it is simple open source to use Epub editing software

With no surprise, only two of the interviewees are already using a structured format (XML, LateX). But a majority declare to be interested in using a structured format in their workflow. Although it should be clarified how easy they think it would be to implement, it is a very

interesting perspective for the OPERAS Working Group on publishing tools.

Despite the statements about the lack of information and skills in this area, some interviewees don't see how OPERAS RI could help them. This is probably due to the constantly shifting environment and the difficulty to identify the actions to take but it shows also how much OPERAS still needs to communicate on its missions. Some needs and suggestions do come up, though, on what would improve their editing/publishing process:

- “Easy to use tools for authors, to create and proofread content within one (not publisher specific) XML-based format.”
- “Training, software and web servers maintenance.”
- “A special web editor like Fidus-Writer for submission, a workflow engine to handle the content's status, an open repository to store the content and to spread the meta-data”

In fact, the distinction of editing/publishing/dissemination tools within an actual workflow is not always easy but the dissemination can be defined by other functions and challenges which we tried to examine more closely.

C. Enrichment and dissemination

1. Metadata

A first minimal metadata enabling an efficient discoverability are the identifiers. Our panel of publishers show that best practices in this matter tend to be widely use also in the SSH community. Almost all of them are providing DOIs for their publications, whatever the size of the publisher. If the technology doesn't seem to be a problem (DOIs are often generated by the publishing software), the fee can be an obstacle to provide DOIs for each document when the publisher is small and isolated.

The author's identifiers like ORCID, on the other hand, are not as well spread. This is obviously due to the fact that they don't have yet the standard status of DOIs but it is also because there are already other identifiers for researchers at another level: international identifiers can coexist with national IDs. In fact, it appears that in this case, more than on the recommendations from every single publisher, the use of international identifiers relies in great part on the policies adopted by other types of stakeholders (national agencies, universities).

When investigating bibliographical and descriptive metadata, we can observe a landscape more disparate, constituted of different groups:

- publishers using no metadata standards
- publishers using only ONIX metadata for distribution
- publishers using tools which generate DublinCore and/or ONIX
- publishers having different sets of metadata

In the first case, it is worth noting the publishers have a workflow based on MS Office and a CMS like Wordpress. In the other cases, the metadata generation can sometime be externalized (for ONIX). But, even if there is a majority of publishers using standards, what strikes the most is that standardization itself is not standardized: there is no common set of metadata standards, there is no majority of DublinCore, ONIX or JATS standards and these coexist with others like NLM/BITS, MARC21. If the responses show that there is already a good basis to adopt best practices in this area in a more general fashion, there are also real challenges to achieve such a purpose. This is what express some suggestions:

- “We use DublinCore and ONIX and have to admit that it took us many years to master them, not in the least because of the variety in data requirement of the parties that take these metadata.”
- “We would appreciate ONIX for any spreading of metadata. To have different formats (OAI, other XMLs for DOI registration...) is obstructive.”

2. Platforms

The survey tried to identify the ways publishers disseminate their content and how they would assess their current solution. Three main groups of publishers emerges from this investigation, with specific comments and issues:

- a major group of publishers (14 out of 21) using and managing their own platforms. They state that this provides “a full editorial freedom, but a limited audience” and also that “it requires personnel and time “;
- another smaller group using both their own platforms and aggregators services: “We want to disseminate our content both through our own platform as well as via aggregated data in other databases. (...) The only important thing is that there should be links and other information available so that the end user can verify the reliability and academic rigor of the material “. Another publisher observed however that “third party aggregator platforms are costly”;
- a last group externalizes dissemination to hosting providers. “By working with a platform provider that offers a customized solution, one benefits from the development roadmap (...). Less satisfying is the ensuing dependency on the capacity and skills of the chosen partner “.

This quick inventory shows that independence is important to our panel, not so much for technological reasons but mainly for intellectual ones. This is however a solution more demanding in terms of skills and time and raises issues for referencing and impact. In that sense, the most significant answer could be the case where a platform is used together with aggregators. Significant especially for the OPERAS RI where each platform could maintain its specificity while sharing common practices and benefiting from central referencing and advanced services.

3. Advanced services

For the advanced services, like in the Spring surveys, we focused on metrics and online annotations which will be implemented through the HIRMEOS project. Where we wanted to assess the level of interest for this specific services, we tried this time to collect more information on the actual practices in this regard.

A large majority (65%) of publishers uses metrics for their publications.

Do you use metrics to track usage of your publications?

The following question about the nature of the metrics collected was very generic (“Which metrics do you use?”) and consequently the answers are altogether about types, tools and sources. As for the types, there are mentions of downloads, views and sometimes regional context. A minority also gathers citations metrics and another minority, not exactly the same, gathers altmetrics. If the main existing tools like Google Analytics and Matomo (former Piwik) are mentioned, other specific tools are used, like OJS plugin or Crossref for the citation metrics. The sources seem to be mainly the publisher’s platforms but they can extend to Twitter/Facebook for altmetrics or platforms like Academia and Researchgate.

It is then obvious there is a rather high diversity of tools and types with a poorly uniform content of the metrics. If we consider also that there is a rough fifty-fifty distribution of publishers thinking they are well informed about the calculation of their metrics and publishers who don’t, we understand that this kind of service still needs improvements and transparency. These challenges will in fact be addressed by the HIRMEOS implementation. This implementation could furthermore take into account the following suggestions:

- “A system that would better fit HSS: by not only charting citations from journals to journals, but also from books to books and from journals to books and vice-versa”.
- “Metrics on how material is used in policy documents, news outlets, blogs, citations

in Web of Science & Scopus”.

About the online annotations, the situation appears to be more clear as only one publisher is currently providing the service (Hypothes.is for Pressbooks). But there is certain amount of publishers very interested or interested with caution by the prospect:

- publishers very interested and considering it: “This could be very powerful, in terms of increased usage and even impact of the publication being used”;
- publishers rather interested but uncertain about researcher’s engagement: “We are not yet sure of its adoption among authors and readers. Authors in many cases do not very actively engage with their work after publication”;
- publishers having considered it but having renounced, mainly for authentication issues: “It is useful if adopted by multiple platforms but confusing to have an extra login requirement on top of platform authentication and personal login”

Just like for the editing/publishing workflow, we can observe for the dissemination process a rather high diversity of practices and advancement. And here also all the challenges are related to some point, as they all have consequences regarding OA publishing capacity to obtain a high level of visibility and research community engagement. The main difference being, in that case, building a common set of practices would perhaps be easier. When it would be difficult or simply not necessary to have everyone using the same publishing workflow, it is possible to start building actual common practices on the existing ground of standards and standards’ awareness that we found in our panel.

D. Multilingualism

In the Spring surveys, we prepared a short set of questions about multilingualism, both for the publication in several languages and for the metadata of the publications. It showed that publication in several languages, by publishers and by researchers, was a very well-spread practice. The survey showed that, alongside with the use of English as science’s *lingua franca* to gain visibility, the SSH community also managed a space for the other languages, mostly European, used by the researchers.

The Autumn survey investigated more in detail the question. The proportion of publications in several languages is here confirmed (83%), as is the proportion for the metadata in several languages (53%).

Do you provide publications in several languages?

Are the metadata also in several languages?

The languages of publication listed by the publishers could be divided by level of size in the following way:

- first, a majority of English as *lingua franca*;
- then, the main European languages;
- finally, specific research community languages.

Languages of publications

From the comments, it appears that every publisher publishes at least in English, but English is not always their main publication language. Furthermore, other languages than English like French or German are perceived as standards in specific fields. The list of languages in the figure can seem rather long and, in fact, only a few publishers publish in more than three languages. This specific cases are perhaps due to particular national situations with more importance given to minority or regional languages. In the overall, languages most spoken at international level (Chinese, Arabic, Portuguese) are not often used as publication languages. Last observation, the cases of translations are very seldom.

Another set of questions allowed for more detailed information on the motivations for publication in several languages.

Do you think that multilingualism in science is important for:

For 76% of the interviewees, multilingualism is important for fostering accuracy in science and 64% think it is important for preserving scientific and cultural vitality of their own language. These results show that multilingualism is clearly motivated and that it is a patent specificity of SSH community. In fact, the way research is conducted in SSH areas appears closely linked to language: multilingualism is not a communicational but an epistemological question. Also, publishers - and researchers through them - clearly identify their own role as an engagement for and with the society they are in.

The publishers made some suggestions for the role OPERAS could play to help to maintain and improve multilingualism:

- “Automated translation of some metadata, e.g. keywords based on a thesaurus”
- “A bilingual publication model would be very welcome”,
- “All systems using metadata should be able to handle Unicode”.

The challenge of mapping metadata mentioned by the first comment will indeed be addressed within OPERAS by the Discovery platform based on Isidore.

E. OPERAS new services

A last question concerned the Certification platform OPERAS is starting to build from the DOAB: “The aim is to provide a certification service for open access monograph publishing platforms: a classification system of peer-reviewing procedures, a list of open licenses, and a tool to manage peer-review descriptions. How do you evaluate this prospect?”.

Like in the Spring surveys, the publishers expressed a high interest with some specific requests:

- that it shouldn’t be a new classification system of the publishers,

- that it shouldn't contain either rates for the PR procedures,
- that it would be good it has the support of large and recognized stakeholders.

Other interesting suggestions confirmed the certification service is on the good path and gave leads to improve it even more:

- “It sounds great to have an entry point for content. As long as you allow for other platforms to hold the same information. (...) A badge system similar to the one used in DOAJ might come in handy to ensure that the quality stamp is available on all local platforms as well.”
- “certification should also evaluate sustainability and/of technical requirements, questions of archiving, monitoring and so on”.

Although some answers showed a sort of fatalism due to a complex and sometimes inadequate ecosystem (on financial, technological or organizational side), the last comments about OPERAS new services shows that the OA publishers have the maturity and willingness to directly improve it.

IV. Libraries

The Spring surveys aimed at having a general overview of the libraries' approach and assessment of open access publishing. It showed a rather high level of involvement but some details, especially technical, were sometimes lacking. The Autumn survey allowed for more detailed information.

Some definitions and specifications are needed in order to better understand the answers. In the libraries' survey, “open access” is generally intended as a delivery specificity, which means it can refer to open access only publishers, or commercial publishers providing also open access, or green OA repositories. At the same time, libraries often use two types of discovery tools: the catalog of their collections (OPAC) and a discovery tool (most of the time a third-party provider). If cataloguing defines the actions made through an OPAC and indexing could be the term for the actions conducted through a discovery tool, they both can be specific steps of the same process.

However, despite the uncertainty this lexical-practical description can make arise, a good summary of the situation could be found in this statement of an interviewee: “We want to give our users immediate access to all resources they need (OA or not OA), and from a discovery/delivery perspective OA is the ideal”.

A. Open access support

A first set of questions investigated the general organization and activity as far as open access publishing is concerned.

What are the resources dedicated to open scholarly communication in your library?

At a large majority (79%), there are human resources dedicated to OA and they are directly installed in the library. This shows that for most libraries open access promotion and support is definitely considered as part of their mission. The importance given to OA implies however questions about the tools used or the training necessary to achieve such a mission.

To complete these first results, the question regarding the OA policies or actions let us see that, even if it is only for an average 50% of the libraries, there is a complete set of actions ranging from engagement to funding for researchers. In fact, the highest result (58%) shows that a certain amount of the libraries in our panel are already participating in collaborative actions for open access. Some of them are engaged in collaborative initiatives (58%, of which a part is already collaborating with OPERAS members) and the numbers prove these collaborations should be extended and improved as they correspond to an actual desire for coordination.

Does your library have specific policies for open access?

Another important role played by the libraries for the promotion of open access is of course the institutional publishing. The responses show that a majority of them (20 out of 36) provides at least one service for institutional publishing and sometimes more than one. A 53% provides a service for publishing journals and a 37% provides an open archive. Books dedicated services appears to be a bit more seldom (26%). Some comments for the “other” category teach us that libraries are also hosting data. This was slightly beyond the scope of this survey but it would be interesting, for the further development of OPERAS RI, to know which data they are hosting and if it is in the SSH area.

If you offer a service for institutional publishing, please specify the type of publication:

In fact, the analysis of the scientific domains covered by the libraries in our panel reveals there is a minority of specialized libraries. A 58% declares their coverage is both in STEM and in SSH. Only a 33% of them has a predominant coverage in SSH. We can infer from these results it is necessary, in order to collaborate better with libraries, to bring the same level of service for SSH OA publishing as in STEM.

In which scientific domains are these publications?

The last question about other forms of support for OA shows that libraries are an essential mediator between the research community and the OA publishers. In fact, passive

information such as bookmarks or links are not the most important solutions. Most of the libraries (63%) provide training directly to their users.

Does your library provide other forms of support for OA publications?

The training aspect does often appear, among others, also in the suggestions for the development of the OPERAS RI:

- “Info kits for social science researchers”
- “Reliable lists of OA journals, basic and general trainings for open access topics, reliable license/rights information about publisher's policies ”
- “Common criteria (metrics to measure research output, criteria to negotiate new publishing and licensing contracts with publishers, monitoring criteria to measure costs and research output)”
- “Support small publishers in getting this infrastructure, and bigger indexes in indexing smaller publishers. Support good infrastructure for OA publishing in smaller languages”

As we can see, the expectations are closely related to the users, that is the researchers, both as authors and as readers. In the first case, there is a request of transparency and centralized information. In the second case, a request for enhanced discoverability.

B. Open access publications management

With the next questions, we tried to see how OA publications were managed by the libraries and especially if there were some specific actions or tools used to integrate them in the

libraries' system.

A majority (63%) of libraries take specific actions to index OA content. The question is mixing cataloguing and indexing in order to avoid too much technical details. Therefore, we have to consider “indexing” in a broad sense.

Does your library index OA publications through its catalog or another discovery tool in order to provide direct access to these publications?

But precisely, like we said in introduction, the situation can vary greatly depending on the type of OA publications we are considering, for instance whether the indexing concerns an institutional repository or selected publications in a database. The indexing of selected publications can be achieved with a specific tool (often cited is Primo by Ex Libris): it offers a list of OA publications to be activated in the catalogue, sometimes with a supplementary manual cataloguing.

In the case of repositories managed by the libraries, the challenge is different because the objective is to make the publication visible in external databases. In this case, as it appears from the answers, the content is indexed externally in third-party generic indexes (Google Scholar, BASE) or in some cases in national indexes.

The same distinction should be made when considering this other aspect of OA management: the metadata. As seen by the libraries, identification metadata (DOI, ORCID) are not an issue for their indexing OA. In the case of activation of OA resources in a database, they are in fact not crucial. But, generally, there is also a good level of satisfaction regarding the bibliographic metadata. More precisely, it appears it is sufficient and standardized enough when there is an intermediary to take care of it: “OAPEN, Knowledge Unlatched, etc. are all delivering these metadata standards. In the ideal world, publishers would supply this data as well...”.

Some answers, however, outline the lack of DOIs and ORCIDs, especially the last one in SSH publications. And the case of green OA can raise a great perplexity: “I see huge problems in that there is no clear licensing, often no ORCID, DOI, etc., or no indication that this is an open access resource”, says one of the interviewees. Another completes by saying that “In UNIMARC there is no specific field for OA”. While this may seem like a detail, it shows how much the specificities of the OA publications still need to be adequately taken into account.

These remarks make us better understand the suggestions about the role of OPERAS in this matter:

- “Aligning publishers, libraries and consortia workflow delivering metadata”
- “The main problem is: who is creating the metadata for new publications? The researchers don't want to bother with it, and the librarians are busy enough with their other tasks
- “Metadata directly from the original source (i.e. the publisher) indexed in openly available global indexes for reuse everywhere”

These suggestions make it clear that something is missing between the multiple small OA publishers and the libraries and this should help to define the role OPERAS intends to play regarding standards and good practices.

C. Open access publishers and providers

1. Discoverability

The questions about discoverability of OA publications show that a majority of libraries are well aware of the existence of the trusted sources DOAJ (84%) and DOAB (64%). In fact, these are the tools they often use to find OA publications and they seem to provide a satisfying service.

However, if we take a closer look at the subject, we come to understand that there is still a lot of information scattered here and there and left to a benevolent serendipity. Leaving apart the fact that most of the time libraries rely on their indexing providers and they rarely look specifically for OA publications, when they do, they have to use other tools with DOAJ/DOAB (like BASE, OAlster) or simply find it difficult, especially as far as SSH is concerned. In fact, one of the interviewee states that they “use different index services (like Scopus, WoS, DOAJ, EHRI, etc.) but WoS and Scopus lack SSH content. And more specifically OA content”.

2. OA publications quality

Another set of questions was designed to specifically examine the service provided by OA publishers and OA publications hosts. It reproduces a series of questions used in the Spring survey and, like then (and perhaps even more abruptly), these questions received very few answers. Of course, we can relate this silence to the fact that libraries rarely have direct contact with publishers or open access providers. However, the truth is that the quality of

OA publications is not measurable through such questions. The real problem is well framed by one interviewee: “The quality is the same as for closed access content if peer review and other technical quality standards are delivered. OA is a matter of distribution and should not be discussed in terms of editorial/quality differences”. Which means, consequently, these quality standards have to be met and certified.

D. Advanced services

In parallel to the current implementations of the HIRMEOS project, libraries were asked whether they use specific metrics for OA publications and the response was always negative. This suggests that this particular aspect of promoting open access should be covered and more widely advocated among libraries. Even if the use of metrics seems somewhat foreign to our panel, an open source tool for metrics/altmetrics will surely raise the interest of libraries.

Like in the Spring survey, the libraries were asked also if they were providing access to publications in several languages and the results are approximately the same with a 67% of “yes”.

Do you provide access to OA publications in several languages?

Given the small number of answers (9), it is not easy to make conclusions but it perhaps means that, generally, publication in several languages is not a priority for the majority and/or it is not specifically related to OA. But when considering the answers of publishers on the same topic, one can ask why something so important for publishers doesn't look as important for the libraries. And in this case also, OPERAS could play the role of intermediary between both the players.

E. OPERAS new services

As in Spring, the libraries were asked for their opinion on the future discovery platform of OPERAS. Based on the existing Isidore platform (<https://www.rechercheisidore.fr>), which is

using various ontologies and controlled vocabularies, this platform could search not only through books and journals but will also index primary data and other research outputs. The prospect raises high interest from the libraries: “We need an international, institutionalized platform for opening up the open access content in the SSH”. They also added interesting suggestions regarding:

- the user’s side: “The user experience is key to making a good platform. Make it simple to use, provide good value to users”.
- the collaborations: “It sounds interesting, but one should take care not to duplicate existing efforts like DOAJ, the Norwegian register etc.”

The Certification platform presented also to the publishers received a unanimous interest, with comments on:

- open access advocacy: “Great idea! Quality management is a key factor in the acceptance of OA by researchers”.
- books’ specifics: “Make sure that you respect the existing peer-review practices for books (they are different from journal peer review)”.
- quality information extension: “I would also be interested in knowing who finances OA-Books, so source of funding would be an interesting category”.

The preliminary observations on definitions are somehow confirmed by the results: the different forms of open access imply different types of involvement in open access. A closer collaboration with the libraries, on the basis of the existing ones, seems a prospect as much expected as promising. And for this purpose, increasing the partnerships with libraries managing also institutional publishing appears to be the adequate starting point.

V. Funders

The survey for the funding agencies was exactly the same as the one we used during Spring. The number of answers (6) is obviously too small to allow for statistical analysis but the details of each one can give us a good idea of the general situation.

All the agencies³ of our panel include open access policies in their programme and these are in some cases available on the web⁴. As it appears from the answers and the policies,

³ See list of the funding agencies in Annex.

⁴ Here are the links of the open access policies the funders indicated:

- FCT: <https://www.fct.pt/acessoaberto/index.phtml.en>
- Fondazione Telethon: <http://www.telethon.it/en/research/for-researchers/open-access>
- Fonds national de la recherche: <http://storage.fnr.lu/index.php/s/9k72EH61fXGL9oX#pdfviewer>
- Nicolaus Copernicus University Library:

the majority of the funding agencies don't include mandates for OA but rather recommendations. It would seem the difference is between foundations, which need to ensure their funding is used properly, and national public agencies, which have also a more generic open access advocacy mission in their country.

Both the green and the gold open access are accepted, even if the recommendations promote the former and add some conditions for the latter. While there can be differences in the accepted delay for self-archiving, the document to archive in a repository is most of the time the preprint (defined as "final peer-reviewed manuscript", i.e. without final proofreading, typesetting or formatting). In case the author chooses to publish in the hybrid model, the funders can provide specific financing for APCs. The conditions in this case can be about the copyright (mention of the funded author at the Fondazione Telethon) or the publisher's business model (avoid double-dipping at the FNR). Recommendations about licenses, on the other hand, appears very seldom. In any case, there are also conditions on the potential embargo period, which is of 6 months in general, with one exception for SSH (accepted 12 months embargo at the FNR).

Regarding the domains covered, precisely, FCT has the same specific embargo policy for SSH content as FNR. As far as the types are concerned, it seems that BPCs are not taken directly into account and that the policies mainly envisage journal publications. Nevertheless, the types listed in the policies can be very wide, for instance at the FCT: "scientific journals, conference proceedings, posters, books and book chapters, monographs, Masters and PhD theses". In fact, we also often find recommendations about the research data: "Where datasets are linked to the publication, these must be made freely available for validation and reuse" (FNR).

About the service providers recommended, especially in the case of self-archiving, the situations and practices are quite different from one agency to another. National agencies can rely on national generic repositories (e.g. RCAAP⁵ in Portugal). In the case of gold OA, specific licenses for open access have sometimes been agreed upon (e.g. Springer Open Choice⁶ in Poland). A particular case is the university library which is managing a complete service from deposit (open repository) to publishing (OJS platform) coupled with an educational environment: this seems to ensure a rather autonomous process of production-dissemination. At another extremity, a topic-based foundation also expressly requires the use of a topic-based repository (PubMed Central⁷ for Fondazione Telethon).

https://www.umk.pl/uczelnia/dokumenty/biuletyn/prawo/?akcja=dokument&typ=Z_Rektora&nr=1&bp=1&rok=2013

⁵ RCCAP website: <https://www.rcaap.pt/>

⁶ Springer Open Choice policy: <http://www.springer.com/gp/open-access/springer-open-choice/springer-compact/springer-open-choice-for-polish-institutions/11027898>

⁷ Pubmed Central website: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/>

In this last case, in fact, the deposit in PubMed is also used to check the mandates have been met by using the PubMed ID generated for the publication. For the same purpose, another agency is using a dedicated tool to track Industrial Property (Clarivate⁸). A last one is using DOAB specifically for SSH content. At the same time, only 2 out of 6 interviewees declare they know and use Funding registry from Crossref. But from the answers, it seems some of the others would be interested to use it as they lack the tools to track the outputs of their funding. In fact, one funding agency describes a situation where a registry based on funding would be helpful: “It would help if you could get a reference without searching the publisher, etc. By boolean search (combining search by author and by title for example), you could then have the reference you were searching for : it can be an article, a book, etc.”.

The set of questions about publishing/disseminating OA platforms show little awareness or interest on the part of the funding agencies but the assessment of their services is generally good. Logically, the expectations towards OPERAS are not so much related to publishing itself but rather to the creation of a centralized infrastructure for OA content: “Generally, we need infrastructure (repositories) for publication and open data. (...) EU needs a coordinated policy towards international publishers to make OA more affordable and available quicker”.

The last two questions were about the Certification platform. As the DOAB will serve as a basis for the future platform, the first question was meant to measure how much the DOAB was known and we found there is a 50/50 distribution between those who know DOAB and the others. This is a rather good basis to communicate about the Certification platform. At the same time, the comments on this platform are sometimes very positive, only some clarifications about usage and features are needed for the project to be fully endorsed.

This specific survey, whether we consider the level of participation or the content of the answers, shows there are still efforts to make to engage funders in OPERAS developments but also that OPERAS services could actually help them fulfil a part of their mission.

VI. Conclusion

A. Open Access variations

As we learned with the Spring surveys and can confirm with these Autumn surveys, there is a general need for rich metadata enabling both visibility and discoverability for open access content. Transparency about publisher’s business models, licenses policies, peer-reviewing processes are also a common request from researchers, publishers, libraries and funders.

However, specific needs of each stakeholder appear clearly from the results: publishers and common practices, libraries and coordination, funders and quality assessment. The

⁸ Clarivate website: <https://clarivate.com>

researchers being, perhaps, a particular case as they would benefit from all these aspects, as authors and as readers.

B. *Ut STEM, SSH...*

Without losing its specificity, open access in SSH can aim to reach the open access standards of STEM. While the publishing quality of SSH OA is generally recognized, some developments are still necessary to fully meet high level requirements: certification service, minimal set of metadata, advanced services and an integrated dissemination system.

The fragmentation characterizing the SSH landscape should not nevertheless be neglected but rather considered as an opportunity to test and spread effective common practices. Typical also of SSH research and deeply motivated, multilingualism is a specific challenge OPERAS has to and wants to address.

C. OPERAS new services

The results of the Autumn surveys confirm that the platforms that will be implemented within OPERAS are validated by the community. The platform Research for Society raised interest from the researchers, and so did the Certification platform and the Discovery platform for the libraries and publishers.

The HIRMEOS implementations of identifiers, as well as advanced services like online annotations and open access metrics also confirm OPERAS and its related project HIRMEOS actually meet the expectations.

D. Coordination challenges

More generally, it appears from the suggestions and comment that the various actors in the field feel a lack of coordination. Some specific efforts have to be done in order to liaise the production, enrichment and dissemination steps of open access in SSH. Alongside with the implementation and provision of new services, it seems necessary that OPERAS endorses this particular mission of helping coordinate not only the requests but also the achievements of each member of the community.

Annex I. Participants

We would like to warmly thank for their participation all our interviewees.

Publishers

- John Benjamins Publishing Company NL
- Edward Elgar Publishing UK
- Ledizioni IT
- BRILL NL
- Amsterdam University Press NL
- Vilnius Gediminas Technical University LT
- Mohr Siebeck GmbH & Co. KG DE
- GLAD! FR
- Septentrio Academic Publishing, UiT The Arctic University of Norway NO
- Hamburg University Press DE
- Bärenreiter-Verlag DE
- ENS EDITIONS FR
- Mappemonde FR
- Public Vocational Training Institute of Patras GR
- Austrian Academy of Sciences AT
- Stockholm University Press SE
- Unisa Press ZA

Libraries

- Biblioteca António Rosa Mendes PT
- Utrecht University NL
- Universitätsbibliothek DE

- Library of Social Sciences and East European Studies DE
- National Library of Science and Technology DE
- Library of the university of Amsterdam NL
- BFH-HAFL Library CH
- Hochschulbibliothek CH
- Media and Information Centre CH
- University Library NL
- VU University Library NL
- UiT The Arctic University of Norway Library NO
- Deutsches Institut für Entwicklungspolitik DE
- Marburg University Library DE
- Biblioteca di Scienze statistiche IT
- BU Pierre Sineux FR
- Bibliothèque universitaire Nantes FR
- Stockholm university library SE

Funding agencies

- Fondazione Telethon IT
- FCT | FCCN PT
- Labex (laboratory of excellence) RESMED FR
- Fonds National de la Recherche LU
- Ministry of Science PL
- Nicolaus Copernicus University Library PL

Annex II. OPERAS surveys form

Publishers

OPERAS (Open Access in the European Research Area through Scholarly Communication) is a consortium of 34 partners from 11 European countries coordinating to promote and support open scholarly communication, particularly in the field of the humanities and social sciences. Its aim is to set up a research infrastructure at the European level and offer Open Science services that are useful for the academic community and global society. To find out more, please see: <http://www.operas-eu.org>

In 2017, OPERAS decided to launch surveys aimed at the different stakeholders in Europe to better understand their needs concerning open scholarly communication. By answering this survey, you will help us to define and establish future services that will really address your needs and drive the academic community towards more and better open science.

General information

This section will help us to know better your organization and your activity, particularly regarding open scholarly communication. OPERAS has launched working groups about business model and best practices and we are willing to gather information on these topics.

What is the name of your organization? *

Which country are you in?

In which scientific domains do you publish?

- Only in SSH
- Mainly in SSH but also in STEM
- Both in SSH and in STEM
- Mainly in STEM but also in SSH
- Only in STEM

Which type of document do you publish (multiple choice possible)?

- Journals only

- Books only Books only
- Both journals and books
- Other

What is your business model (multiple choice possible) ?

- Revenues on sales
- OA Institutional funding
- Library support
- Books processing charges / Article processing charges
- Other

Which service, in your opinion, could OPERAS provide to help you develop a sustainable business model for open access publishing?

Is your Open Access policy limited to specific types of publications, formats, with an embargo? Why?

Do you have a free licensing policy and which are the free licenses you are using?

In your opinion, what are the main obstacles to using the most permissive free licenses for your publications?

Publishing workflow

This technical section is meant to provide an inventory of the solutions, the issues and the needs regarding the publishing process. Your input will help OPERAS to develop useful services to academic publishers in the future.

Are you satisfied with your current production workflow? If not, specify the difficulties you experience and the improvements needed.

Which publishing software(s) do you use?

What are your expectations regarding your publishing tool(s) and was it easy to find the right one(s)?

Could you briefly explain the choice you finally made?

In your publishing workflow, what are the main formats for input data/documents?

- DOC, DOCX
- ODT
- PDF
- XML
- XML-TEI
- Other

In your publishing workflow, what are the main formats for output data/documents?

- HTML
- PDF
- EPUB
- MOBI
- Other

Do you think you should have a more standardized publishing workflow, for instance having a central format like XML for submission, edition and publication?

In your opinion, which kind of help regarding the publishing tools OPERAS could provide to academic publishers, especially as far as SSH content is concerned?

Enrichment and dissemination

Based on questions about metadata and advanced services like metrics and online annotation, this section investigates different aspects of enhanced reading, searching, and measurement.

If you use persistent and interlinked IDs for documents (e.g. DOI) or authors (e.g. ORCID), could you briefly explain how you chose them? If you don't use them, please explain the reasons.

Do you use metadata standards (e.g. DublinCore, METS, ONIX, etc.) to describe your publications and can you easily use them? *

Based on your experience, what needs to be improved regarding identification or descriptive metadata and how these improvements could be achieved?

If you disseminate your content on your own platform, can you expose briefly the strengths and the weaknesses of this model?

If you outsource dissemination of your content on Internet, can you state what is satisfying or not satisfying about your service provider?

Do you use metrics to track usage of your publications?

Which metrics do you use?

Do you consider yourself well informed about the nature and calculation of these metrics?

Which other kind of metrics would be more useful for your activity?

How would you consider an online application allowing users to add annotations to the publications (like for instance Hypothes.is)?

Multilingualism

Multilingualism is often a characteristic of the research and the publishing in the Social Sciences and Humanities field. OPERAS wants to investigate further this aspect to find out how it should be a part of the research infrastructure services.

Do you provide publications in several languages?

Could you briefly state which are the different languages you are using and why you are publishing

in these different languages?

Are you publishing mainly in English or in a national or a regional language? Are you publishing in languages that are not English or spoken in your country?

Are the metadata also in several languages?

Based on your experience, what would help you to improve the publication in several languages? Which specific service of OPERAS would you expect for this purpose?

Based on your experience, what would allow you to provide the publication in several languages? Would they be technical or organizational solutions?

Based on your perception of the expectations authors and institutions have, do you think that multilingualism in science is important for: *

- Preserving the scientific and cultural vitality of your own language?
- Fostering accuracy in science (especially in what pertains to linguistic, literary, cultural and interpretative issues)?
- Stimulating openness to diversity?
- Establishing complementary networks?

OPERAS and new services

In order to support open access dissemination in the SSH, OPERAS is planning to provide wide-ranging integrated services. OPERAS will provide a single access point in Europe to a vast library of well-structured, easily searchable and validated content in SSH.

The OPERAS project is planning to support the development of the DOAB (<http://www.doabooks.org>). The aim is to provide a certification service for open access monograph publishing platforms: a classification system of peer-reviewing procedures, a list of open licenses, and a tool to manage peer-review descriptions. How do you evaluate this prospect?

Would you be interested in joining the OPERAS consortium and one of its working groups (<http://operas-eu.org/aboutoperas/working-groups>)?

Libraries

General information

What is the name of your library?

Which institution are you affiliated to?

Which country are you in?

Open Access activity

This section will help us to know better your organization and your activity, particularly regarding open scholarly communication.

Could you give some indications about the resources dedicated to open scholarly communication in your library?

- There are human resources dedicated to open access promotion and support at University level.
- There are human resources dedicated to open access promotion and support in your Library.
- There are human resources trained but not dedicated to promote and support open access publications.
- Other

Does your library have specific policies for open access? Specify whenever possible. *

- Your University has signed the Berlin Declaration.
- Your institution (University or Library) has a mandate for Open Access.
- Your library participates in collaborative initiatives for the development of open access (e.g. Knowledge Unlatched, OpenEdition Freemium).
- Your library has APC and/or BPC funds available for researchers.

If your library offers a service for institutional publishing, please specify the type of publication:

- Journals
- Books
- Open Archive
- Other

In which scientific domains are these publications?

- Only in SSH Only in SSH
- Mainly in SSH but also in STEM Mainly in SSH but also in STEM
- Both in SSH and in STEM Both in SSH and in STEM
- Mainly in STEM but also in SSH Mainly in STEM but also in SSH
- Only in STEM Only in STEM

Open Access in your library

Alongside with open access policies, we would like to know which more practical actions your library has to promote, flag or index open access content. The collected information will help OPERAS to find out which services can be provided to make these actions more efficient.

Does your library index OA publications through its catalog or another discovery tool in order to provide direct access to these publications? *

Could you specify by which actions you promote or flag OA publications in your catalog or discovery tool? Please describe the discovery tool.

Which types of open access documents do you index?

- OA journals
- OA books
- Open Archives
- Other

Do you include OA documents from SSH disciplines in your catalog/index?

Does your library provide other forms of support for OA publications? Specify whenever possible.

- Bookmarks
- Links
- Documentation
- Training
- Conferences

Based on your experience, which kind of services OPERAS could provide to help you improve your service provision for OA publications?

Open Access publications' sources

The open access landscape, especially in SSH, appears rather fragmented in many stakeholders, types of publication or peer-reviewing processes. We would like to know your perception of the current open access offer on the market and its quality.

Could you explain briefly how you find OA journals and books to mention on your website or to integrate in your catalog?

Do you know and do you use DOAJ and/or DOAB directories for these purposes or for the users of your library?

Does it seem easy to you to find OA publications, especially in SSH?

As far as publishers of OA content in SSH are concerned, could you precise your level of satisfaction in the table below?

Please choose the appropriate response for each item:

Not satisfactory / Not really satisfactory / Rather satisfactory / Very satisfactory

- Scientific quality and peer reviewing:
- Editing quality:
- Publishing formats:

- Metrics provided:

Do you have a suggestion or comment to share regarding the quality of OA publishers in SSH?

Regarding the providers of OA publications in SSH, could you precise your level of satisfaction?

Please choose the appropriate response for each item:

Not satisfactory / Not really satisfactory / Rather satisfactory / Very satisfactory

- Information on their service:
- Service availability:
- Editing quality:
- Publishing formats:
- Metrics provided:

Do you have a suggestion or comment to share regarding the quality of providers for OA publications in SSH?

Open Access advanced services

Based on questions about metadata and advanced services like metrics and online annotation, this section investigates different aspects of enhanced reading, searching, and measurement.

Do you think there is a lack of identification metadata (DOI, ORCID, etc.) in open access publications and is it an obstacle to index them in your catalog?

Do you think there is a lack of descriptive metadata standards (MARC, DublinCore, etc.) in open access publications and is it an obstacle to index them in your catalog? *

Do you have any suggestion or comment about possible improvements regarding metadata practices for OA publications, especially in SSH? Which role could have OPERAS in this perspective?

Do you produce or receive specific metrics for the OA publications present in your catalog and do you find them useful?

Do you have any suggestion on metrics or altmetrics which could improve the OA service provision?

Do you provide access to OA publications in several languages and do you manage metadata description and search in several languages?

Do you have any suggestion or comment on how OPERAS could make it easier for you to manage publications in several languages?

OPERAS new services

In order to support open access dissemination in the SSH, OPERAS is planning to provide wide-ranging integrated services. OPERAS will provide a single access point in Europe to a vast library of well-structured, easily searchable and validated content in SSH.

The OPERAS project is planning to implement a discovery platform dedicated to open access in Social Sciences and Humanities. This platform could search not only through books and journals but will also index primary data and other research outputs. The platform will be based on the existing Isidore platform (<https://www.rechercheisidore.fr>), which is using various ontologies and controlled vocabularies to enhance resources description and discoverability. How would you evaluate this prospect and what are your suggestions in this regard?

The OPERAS project is also planning to support the development of the DOAB (<http://www.doabooks.org>). The aim is to provide a certification service for open access monograph publishing platforms: a classification system of peer-reviewing procedures, a list of open licences, and a tool to manage peer-review descriptions. How do you evaluate this prospect?

Funding agencies

Your information

What is the name of your organisation?

Which country are you in?

Your action for open access

Does your funding programme include open access policies?

Could you give us a link to a page where these open access policies are described?

Does your funding programme include open access mandates?

Could you give us a link to a page where these open access mandates are described?

Does your funding open access policies or mandates have special provisions for:

- Journals
- Books
- Social Sciences and Humanities

Common standards and good practices

Considering the fragmentation of services in open access SSH, Operas's primary goals are to use common standards and advocate for common good practices. The standards will help develop interoperability and discoverability; good practices will ensure the quality of open access publishing.

Are you using or recommending specific services as far as SSH OA is concerned (dedicated repositories, open access publishers, etc.)?

In order to check that your Open Acces policies or mandates have been respected, do you use dedicated services for SSH and which ones?

OPERAS is implementing Funding registry identifiers (see: <https://www.crossref.org/services/funder-registry/>) to identify the funders of the books published by its consortium. Do you already know and use Funding registry identifiers and do you think they are useful to you?

Based on your experience, how would you evaluate the OA services partly or specifically dedicated to the SSH that you have used or recommended?

Please choose the appropriate response for each item:

Not satisfactory / Not really satisfactory / Rather satisfactory / Satisfactory

- European generic repositories
- National generic repositories
- Dedicated repositories for SSH
- SSH OA journal publishers
- SSH OA book publishers

Which kind of improvements of SSH open access services OPERAS could provide that would help you to fulfil your mission?

OPERAS new services

In order to support open access dissemination in the SSH, OPERAS is planning to provide wide-ranging integrated services. OPERAS will provide a single access point in Europe to a vast library of well-structured, easily searchable and validated content in SSH. They will cover peer-reviewing certification, enhanced harvesting and indexing, and a dedicated platform for researchers and the general public to work together.

OAPEN, a member of the OPERAS consortium, handles the Directory of Open Access Books (DOAB) which references open access books. Do you already know and use the DOAB service ?

- We know what it is and we use it We know what it is and we use it
- We know what it is but we never use it We know what it is but we never use it
- We don't know what it is We don't know what it is

The OPERAS project is planning to support the development of the DOAB (<http://www.doabooks.org>). The aim is to provide a certification service for open access monograph publishing platforms: a classification system of peer-reviewing procedures, a list of open licenses, and a tool to manage peer-review descriptions. How do you evaluate this prospect?

The OPERAS project is also planning to implement a discovery platform dedicated to SSH OA. This platform could search not only through books and journals but also index primary data and research outputs. The platform will be based on the existing Isidore platform (<https://www.rechercheisidore.fr>), which is using various ontologies and controlled vocabularies to

enhance resources description and discoverability. based on your current activities, how would you evaluate this prospect?

Do you have any suggestion for a service in OA SSH that OPERAS could develop to facilitate your mission?

